

Teacher Classroom Environment in Relation to Student Motivation and Preparedness

Jayson B. Dijon

Abstract. The study unfolded the relationship between teachers' classroom environment and students' motivation and preparedness for high school in Governor Generoso District, Davao Oriental Schools Division. The study used a descriptive-correlational research design, utilizing an adapted survey instrument to gather responses from the randomly selected teacher respondents. Data collected were treated using Mean scores with descriptive interpretation, Pearson r , and Simple Linear Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that the extent of teachers' classroom environment shows that safe and inclusive space, organized learning environment, and teacher-student relationships are often manifested. In contrast, communication feedback and consistent classroom management are sometimes manifested. At the same time, the extent of students' motivation and preparedness shows that academic confidence, self-advocacy skills, and goal setting were often manifested. In contrast, resilience, adaptability, time management, and organizational skills sometimes manifest. A significant correlation exists between teachers' classroom environment and students' motivation and preparedness. Domains of teachers' classroom environment in terms of teacher-student relationship, safe and inclusive space, organized learning environment, consistent classroom management, and communication and feedback significantly influence students' motivation and preparedness.

KEY WORDS

1. Teachers' classroom environment
2. preparedness for high school
3. students' motivation

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1. Introduction

The classroom environment shapes students' motivation and preparedness as they transition to high school. A well-crafted and supportive classroom environment is conducive to effective teaching and learning and sets the stage for students' readiness to face the challenges of high school. Schools offer regular access to students throughout their developmental years. A school that implements and maintains an effective program may improve the overall school climate and, in so doing, have a positive effect on youth behavior both during and after school hours. The lack of positive feelings for and identification with one's school is directly related to juvenile delinquency. Globally, formal classroom systems can be found in every citadel of learning in all countries, be it developed or developing countries, depending on the types, shapes, classes, and academic environments in which they are situated. According to

Adesua (2019), the classroom environment is an important, influential, and effective instrument of socialization where learners from different socioeconomic backgrounds come together to learn. Classrooms are found in educational institutions, including public and private schools, home schools, corporations, and religious and humanitarian organizations. Different types of indoor and outdoor classrooms are used for lessons that require specific resources or a vocational approach. Classrooms can range from small groups of five or six to big classrooms with hundreds of students. A large classroom is also called a lecture hall. Many consider instructional approaches that combine social and thinking skills to effectively enhance students' abilities, attitudes, and behaviors inconsistent with substance abuse and other delinquent behavior (Northeast Center for the Application of Prevention Technologies 2018). Further, interventions involving classroom organization, management, and instructional strategies attempt to promote the protective factors that promote opportunities for active participation in learning, skills to establish positive social relationships and bonding with school and prosocial peers. The classroom environment is an important motivating factor that makes or mars the teaching and learning process. The curriculum or the content of the school syllabus is being implemented mainly within the four walls of the classroom through professional teachers who are the curriculum implementers. It appears that the quality of teaching would likely affect the learning of many secondary school subjects and learning programs; this may result from the state of the classroom environment (Özüdogru, 2022). In the Philippines, the teacher's classroom environment plays a crucial role in shaping students' educational experiences. A well-crafted classroom environment is conducive to effective teaching and learning and influences students' motivation and preparedness as they progress through their academic journey. Educators in

the Philippines play a vital role in preparing students for the challenges they will face as they progress through the Philippine education system and, ultimately, contribute to developing a well-rounded, informed, and responsible citizenry in the country. As they navigate the complexities of the Philippine educational landscape, teachers continue to refine their classroom environments to meet the evolving needs of their students and society (Cardinal, 2021). The quality of teaching and learning in any establishment determines academic excellence. For effective teaching and learning processes to occur within the school environment, there must be provision for required learning aids such as a conducive school physical environment, a well-painted classroom, adequate chairs, moderate distance from an industrial area to prevent unwanted noise, and a well-experienced teacher. Various teachers' personal experiences across the globe indicated that different criteria needed to be seriously put into consideration when it comes to achieving the desired educational goals and objectives in a classroom environment (Linnenbrink-Garcia, 2022). One of the fundamental aspects of the classroom environment in the Philippines is the quality of teacher-student relationships: renowned Philippine educator and author Jose Maria C. San Andres emphasized the importance of fostering positive connections with students. In the Philippine culture, respect for authority figures, including teachers, is highly valued. Building solid and respectful relationships with students can contribute to a positive and harmonious classroom atmosphere. These relationships can boost students' motivation, as they feel valued and supported. The classroom environment in Governor Generoso, Davao Oriental, reflects this locality's unique cultural and educational context. Just as in any other region, the teacher's classroom environment plays a vital role in shaping students' learning experiences. A well-structured and supportive classroom set-

ting is essential for effective teaching and learning, motivating students, and preparing them for future challenges. Engaging with the local community is an integral aspect of the classroom environment in this setting. Teachers often work closely with community leaders, parents, and regional organizations to create a holistic learning experience. Creating an effective classroom environment in Governor Generoso, Davao Oriental, is a dynamic and context-specific endeavor. It involves building positive teacher-student relationships, respecting local culture and values, engaging with the community, implementing effective classroom management, and incorporating the local context into the curriculum. Local educators continue to play a pivotal role in shaping the classroom environment to meet the unique needs of students and the community. As they navigate the complexities of this local educational landscape, teachers in Governor Generoso contribute to the development of informed, culturally grounded, and community-oriented individuals who are prepared to face future challenges.

2. Methodology

This chapter contains the processes and steps in conducting the study. These include selecting the study's design, the respondents and sampling method, the research instruments to be used in data gathering, the procedure, the ethical considerations, and lastly, the data analysis. These steps are considered essential to ensure appropriateness and correctness and to produce sound data process collection, analysis, and interpretation.

2.1. Research Design—The study used the non-experimental, descriptive - correlational research design, which investigates the degree to which two or more variables are related. It does not involve the manipulation of any variables but rather measures and analyses the existing relationship between them (Creswell, 2014). In this study, correlational research design can examine the relationship between the extent of School Heads' role in authentic leadership and Teachers' organizational commitment. According to Creswell (2014), a descriptive-correlational research design describes and explains the relationship between two or more variables. The main goal of this type of research design is to identify the relationship between variables, and it can be used to make predictions about future events. Descriptive-correlational research designs are used to describe the relationships between variables. Researchers collect data on two or more variables and then analyze the data to determine if there is a relationship between them. This type of research is used to generate hypotheses for future studies (Campbell Stanley, 1963). Finally, a descriptive-correlational research design can be valuable when experimental manipulation of variables is not possible or ethical. For example, it may be unethical to manipulate variables such as age, gender, or medical condition to examine their effects on other variables. In such cases, a descriptive-correlational design can provide a valuable alternative for investigating the relationships between variables of interest without requiring manipulation or control of those variables. In this study, the relationship between establishing a classroom environment among Grade 6 teachers and learners' motivation and preparedness in the Gov. Generoso District is assumed to be associated. Thus, the measure of the research design is appropriate for this study.

2.2. Research Respondents—Respondents of the study were the Elementary School Teachers of Governor Generoso District, Davao Oriental Schools Division. He used the Raosoft sample size calculator, where 80 respondents were

taken randomly from each respective School in the Governor Generoso District's Elementary Schools. Once randomly determined, the respondents were informed through online platform and face-to-face, considering the availability of the Wifi Connections; they were likewise oriented about the purpose and importance of the study and its contribution to their professional development status. These teacher-respondents were the teachers who were actively and directly involved in most of the school's activities relevant to effective curriculum management and delivery through learning action cell sessions where learners' performance, and other related activities to prepare the learners in high school life and to support programs, projects, and activities in line with the implementation plan as directed by DepED mandates under MATATAG Agenda. Moreover, teachers with skills in strategizing the simplification of operational processes and management in school, apart from curriculum implementation and delivery, are likewise trying to improve the system to achieve performance given the financial management system. They are qualified for they are expected to have performed and contributed to the betterment of the schools and the parents' participation given new regular learning system during SY 2023-2024. Further, they have frequently engaged in various seminars and trainings in the school management and curriculum development delivery system. Moreover, assumptions in the respective schedule of classes during data collection were explicitly discussed with the respondents, and even observance of health protocol was strictly im-

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—The data-gathering procedure within a research project involves a series of critical steps, and among them is the ethical process of obtaining permission to conduct the study. This step is integral to upholding core principles of re-

plemented based on Executive Order 31 S 2020 to avoid possible and lower the risk of contamination.

2.3. Research Instrument—This research study used the adapted instrument from reviewed literature and related studies. The researcher took time gathering and reading reviews of related literature to come up with concepts for the content that support the instrument and its corresponding strands in articulating the set of question items, reducing threats to validity. Items were adapted from the reviewed literature, as the authors argued. The survey questionnaire had two parts: determining the extent of the classroom environment in terms of teacher relationships, safe and inclusive space, organized learning environment, consistent classroom management, and communication and feedback. Likewise, the second part of the survey measured the extent of student motivation and preparedness in terms of academic confidence, time management and organizational skills, goal setting, self-advocacy skills and reliance and adaptability. Further, the survey statements were subjected to a test-retest or validity and reliability testing using Cronbach Alpha at a .05 level of confidence. They generated an alpha Cronbach of 0.899, which means that an 89.9 percent level of confidence in the validity and reliability of the survey statement constructs (Pallant 2010). The questionnaire used a 5-point Likert scale to determine the extent of the classroom environment; the scale, descriptive rating, and interpretation are provided below:

spect, transparency, and responsible research conduct. The statements are based on the policies and guidelines of the Rizal Memorial Colleges; as part of the request, researchers articulate their intentions for data collection, analysis, and dissemination, illustrating how these

Classroom Environment Scale

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The classroom environment is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The classroom environment is often-times manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The classroom environment is some-times manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The classroom environment is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The classroom environment is not manifested

align with the overall research goals. This correspondence should address any concerns or questions anticipated from recipients, alongside assurances regarding ethical safeguards, confidentiality measures, and the study’s potential benefits. The formal permission request is then made, explicitly seeking authorization to proceed and emphasizing the significance of their support for the research’s success. Permission to conduct the study. On October 2023, before collecting data, the researcher must obtain permission from the appropriate authorities, such as the research adviser and the Dean of the Rizal Memorial Colleges, and the top management of DepEd Davao Oriental Division through the channel. This permission-seeking process typically involves submitting a research proposal with information about the study design, procedures, and potential risks and benefits. The researcher provided information about the purpose and goals of the study and how the data will be collected, analyzed, and reported. In addition, in January 2024, the researcher ensured that all participants were fully informed about the study and their rights and that they provided informed consent before participating.

Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. In the first week of April 2024, the researcher ensured the accuracy and completeness of data, and the distribution and retrieval of questionnaires were conducted in a standardized and systematic manner. She considered several critical conditions during her research process. First, she identified the appropriate target population for the study, ensuring that the questionnaire was distributed exclusively to individuals who met the inclusion criteria. Informed consent was obtained from all participants before distributing the questionnaire, which involved providing information about the study’s purpose, goals, and potential risks and benefits. To maintain confidentiality, the researcher ensured that the questionnaire was anonymous, with no identifying information linked to respondents, and that the collected data was used solely for the study’s purposes. Additionally, she standardized the questionnaire distribution process to guarantee that all participants received identical instructions and had equal opportunities to complete it. Participants were given ample time to complete the questionnaire and were encouraged to ask any questions regarding the process. Finally,

Student Motivation and Preparedness Scale

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The student motivation and preparedness is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The student motivation and preparedness is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The student motivation and preparedness is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The student motivation and preparedness is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The student motivation and preparedness is not manifested

the researcher collected the completed questionnaires promptly and organized to ensure the data was recovered and found. Collation and statistical treatment of data. The general conditions for the collation and statistical treatment of data as part of the data-gathering procedure include ensuring that the data is accurate and free from errors by checking and validating it, and that it is complete, encompassing all necessary information to avoid incorrect conclusions. The data must be consistent, with no contradictions or discrepancies, as inconsistencies can cause confusion and inaccuracies. It should be relevant to the research question or problem to prevent

misleading conclusions and should be collected and analyzed in a timely manner to maintain its usefulness and accuracy. Objectivity is crucial, meaning the data should be free from bias or personal opinions to ensure validity, as biased data can skew results. Validity is essential to ensure the data measures what it is intended to measure, while reliability ensures the data can be replicated or reproduced, both of which are vital to avoid incorrect conclusions. Finally, the data should undergo appropriate statistical analysis to identify patterns, trends, and relationships, which can uncover significant insights and relationships within the data.

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—Ethical considerations are pivotal in ensuring the integrity and respect for individuals’ rights within research and educational endeavors. In the context of voluntary participation, ethics underscore the principle that individuals should willingly and without coercion choose to participate in any activity or study. This ethical guideline emphasizes informed consent, which involves providing participants with comprehensive in-

formation about the activity or research’s nature, purpose, risks, and benefits. Social Value Research plays an essential role in society, particularly in fostering collaboration and motivation among elementary educators. This study seeks to investigate the social issue of digital reading and comprehension among students, emphasizing how teachers’ effectiveness impacts this process. The outcomes of this research could provide valuable insights for policymakers and

educational authorities, allowing them to design programs and initiatives that enhance student learning. Furthermore, social value serves as a critical standard for conducting ethical research. This viewpoint underscores the anticipated benefits that a research intervention may bring to the well-being of society or specific communities. Ethical considerations are crucial for protecting the rights and welfare of research participants. Key ethical concerns include ensuring participant anonymity, refraining from collecting personally identifiable information, and safeguarding the confidentiality of participants' identities.

Voluntary Participation Ensures that individuals have the autonomy to make decisions based on their values, beliefs, and interests. This approach safeguards against undue influence, manipulation, or pressure that might compromise the validity and ethical foundation of the endeavor. This further fosters a sense of ownership and engagement among respondents, allowing them to contribute to their experience actively. It also upholds the principles of respect and human dignity by recognizing that each individual's consent is paramount. By adhering to ethical considerations regarding voluntary participation, the researcher cultivates an environment that is built on trust, transparency, and the fundamental values of moral conduct.

Privacy and Confidentiality In this study, upholding privacy entails respecting individuals' boundaries and ensuring that their personal data is collected, stored, and used solely for the intended purpose with their informed consent. In contrast, confidentiality requires that any information shared in trust remains secure and undisclosed to unauthorized parties. This involves implementing secure data storage, anonymizing information whenever possible, and obtaining explicit consent for any information shared publicly.

Informed Consent All participants in this study were provided with a clear explanation of the research procedures and goals, and any

potential risks or benefits associated with participation. Informed consent involves providing individuals with comprehensive and understandable information about the nature, purpose, procedures, risks, benefits, and potential outcomes of an activity or study. This empowers individuals to make informed decisions based on their own values and preferences. Within the informed consent process, individuals should be allowed to ask questions and seek clarification before voluntarily agreeing to participate. The information must be presented in a language and format that is accessible and understandable to the participants, ensuring they fully grasp the implications of their involvement.

Risks and Benefits In research, ethical guidelines dictate that researchers must carefully evaluate any risks that participants might encounter during their involvement. This includes physical, psychological, emotional, and social risks. The principle of beneficence guides researchers to minimize these risks to the greatest extent possible while maximizing potential benefits. Ethical considerations mandate that participants are fully informed about any identified risks, enabling them to make informed decisions about their involvement. Ethical considerations regarding benefits are integral to ensuring the well-being and integrity of individuals engaged in research, education, or professional interactions. Ethical practice entails transparently communicating potential benefits to participants so they can make informed decisions about their involvement. Furthermore, researchers, educators, and professionals are responsible for upholding these benefits while ensuring that they outweigh any potential risks. In research, identifying potential benefits for participants is crucial.

Plagiarism

Ethical considerations surrounding plagiarism are vital in upholding academic and professional work's integrity, honesty, and originality. Plagiarism involves presenting someone else's ideas, words, or work as one's own with-

out proper attribution. In research endeavors, plagiarism compromises the reliability and credibility of findings, which can have far-reaching consequences for scientific progress and public trust. Adequate attribution of sources is essential to maintain the accuracy and originality of ideas. Plagiarism detection tools are also commonly used to ensure the authenticity of written work.

Fabrication Fabrication involves the deliberate creation or alteration of data, information, or findings with the intent to deceive or mislead others. This practice undermines the foundations of honesty, transparency, and authenticity, which are vital to the pursuit of knowledge and ethical conduct. In research, fabrication erodes the credibility of scientific inquiry and compromises the reliability of findings. Fabricated data can lead to incorrect conclusions, wasted resources, and the misdirection of future research efforts, ultimately hindering the advancement of knowledge. Ethical considerations concerning falsification are essential for maintaining the credibility, honesty, and reliability of research, education, and professional interactions. Falsification involves manipulating, altering, or distorting data, results, or information to deceive or misrepresent the truth. This practice undermines the principles of transparency, accuracy, and intellectual integrity that underpin ethical conduct. In research, falsification undermines the foundation of scientific inquiry by distorting the truth and compromising the validity of findings. Falsified data can lead to incorrect conclusions, skewed interpretations, and a distortion of the knowledge-building process, ultimately undermining the trustworthiness of research outcomes.

Conflict of Interest

In research, identifying and addressing conflicts of interest is essential to ensure the credibility and impartiality of study outcomes. Transparent disclosure of potential conflicts helps maintain the objectivity of research findings and

the trust of the broader scientific community. Ethical practice demands proactively identifying and managing conflicts of interest to prevent undue influence, bias, or compromise in decision-making processes. Individuals must take steps to disclose potential conflicts openly and make choices that prioritize the welfare of all stakeholders involved.

Deceit Ethical considerations regarding deceit are crucial for upholding honesty, integrity, and trust in various contexts, including research, education, and professional interactions. Deceit involves intentionally misleading or withholding information to manipulate perceptions, decisions, or actions, undermining the principles of transparency and respect fundamental to ethical conduct. In research, deceit undermines the credibility of findings and the trustworthiness of the scientific process. Falsifying or concealing data, methods, or results can lead to inaccurate conclusions, damaging the progress of knowledge and eroding the trust that the public places in research outcomes.

Permission from the Organization/Location

Obtaining permission from the organization or location where research, education, or activities take place is a fundamental ethical consideration that ensures respect, transparency, and responsible conduct. Seeking permission is essential when engaging in activities that might impact the organization's resources, reputation, or individuals associated with it. In research, gaining permission from relevant institutions or organizations is crucial for conducting studies that involve data collection, observations, or interactions with participants. This demonstrates a commitment to ethical research practices, informed consent, and respect for individuals' rights.

Authorship To maintain fairness, accountability, and transparency in research, publication, and collaborative endeavors, the researcher respects the intellectual contributions of individuals, ensuring they receive proper recogni-

tion for their efforts. Ethical authorship in research involves accurately attributing contributions based on substantial intellectual and practical involvement in the project. Proper credit reflects the principles of honesty, integrity, and respect for others' work. Addressing authorship ethically upholds values such as accountability,

fairness, and integrity. By following guidelines that ensure accurate representation of contributions, we maintain the integrity of scholarly work, foster a culture of equitable collaboration, and uphold the trust of the academic and research community.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—Mean scores and standard deviation were used to address statement problems posed in number one (1) extent of teacher's classroom environment, and statement problem number two (2) on the extent of student motivation and preparedness in Governor Generoso District, Davao Oriental Schools Division. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson-r was used to determine its strength/direction significant relationship be-

tween teacher's classroom environment and student motivation and preparedness. Simple Linear Regression analysis was used to address problem number 4, on the indicators of classroom environment that significantly influence student motivation and preparedness (Pallant, 2000) (Gujarati, 2000). All data processing and analysis were performed using Jeffrey's Statistics Amazing Program (JASP) version 0.12.20. Discussions and interpretations followed when results were yielded.

3. Results and Discussion

This section focuses on presenting, analyzing, and interpreting the collected data. It includes both tabular and textual formats to enhance the depth of analysis and facilitate the extraction of meaningful implications. Additionally, this section provides further evidence to substantiate the hypothesis proposed.

Summary of the Extent of Teachers' Classroom Environment Table 1 shows the summary of the extent of teachers' classroom environment. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Safe And Inclusive Space (3.56), Organized Learning Environment (3.56) and Teacher-

Student Relationship (3.54) are oftentimes manifested, while, Communication And Feedback (2.80) and Consistent Classroom Management (2.61) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.21 denotes extent of teachers' classroom environment is sometimes manifested, thus, moderately extensive.

The extent of teachers' impact on the classroom environment is profound and encompasses various elements that collectively shape the learning experience. Teachers play a pivotal role in setting the tone for the classroom, influencing factors such as the atmosphere, dynamics, and overall culture of the learning space. The physical arrangement of the classroom, instructional

strategies employed, and the teacher's approach to classroom management all contribute to the overall environment. A well-designed and organized classroom, coupled with engaging teaching methods, can enhance student focus and participation. Additionally, teachers are responsible for creating an inclusive and respectful atmosphere that caters to diverse learning styles

Table 1. Summary of the Extent of Teachers’ Classroom Environment

Teachers’ Classroom Environment	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Safe And Inclusive Space	3.56	Extensive
Organized Learning Environment	3.56	Extensive
Teacher-Student Relationship	3.54	Extensive
Communication And Feedback	2.80	Moderately Extensive
Consistent Classroom Management	2.61	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.21	Moderately Extensive

and backgrounds.

Table 2 shows the summary of the extent of students’ motivation and preparedness. The result is focused on the highest and lowest mean ratings of indicators which are as follows: Academic Confidence (3.67), Self-Advocacy Skills (3.59) and Goal Setting (3.57) are oftentimes

manifested, while; Resilience And Adaptability (3.39) and Time Management And Organizational Skills (2.95) are sometimes manifested. The overall mean rating of 3.43 denotes extent of students’ motivation and preparedness is oftentimes manifested, thus, extensive.

Table 2. Summary of the Extent of Students’ Motivation and Preparedness

Students’ Motivation and Preparedness	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Academic Confidence	3.67	Extensive
Time Management And Organizational Skills	2.95	Moderately Extensive
Goal Setting	3.57	Extensive
Self-Advocacy Skills	3.59	Moderately Extensive
Resilience And Adaptability	3.39	Moderately Extensive
Overall Mean	3.43	Extensive

The extent of students’ motivation and preparedness is pivotal in determining their success and engagement within an educational setting. Motivation serves as a driving force behind a student’s willingness to learn, participate, and persist in the face of challenges. A motivated student is more likely to be proactive in their

studies, exhibit a positive attitude toward learning, and demonstrate a higher level of commitment to academic tasks. Preparedness, on the other hand, involves not only the possession of necessary materials but also mental readiness for the learning process (Ginevra, et.al, 2018). Students who come to class well-prepared are

better equipped to grasp new concepts, actively participate in discussions, and efficiently complete assignments. The extent of students' motivation and preparedness is influenced by various factors, including personal interest in the subject matter, perceived relevance of the material, and the learning environment itself. Educators can play a crucial role in fostering motivation by employing engaging teaching methods, providing real-world connections to the curriculum, and offering constructive feedback. Additionally, promoting a culture of accountability and emphasizing the value of preparation can contribute to students' overall readiness for the educational journey. In essence, the extent to which students are motivated and prepared directly impacts the quality of their learning experience and lays the foundation for academic achieve-

ment (Brewer, et.al 2022).

Significant Relationship between Teachers' Classroom Environment and Students' Motivation and Preparedness

It can be depicted that Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between teachers' classroom environment ($r=0.870$; $p<.001$) and students' motivation and preparedness. Table 3 revealed the significant relationship between teachers' classroom environment and students' motivation and preparedness. It provides information that the posed null hypothesis stating that there is no significant correlation between teachers' classroom environment and students' motivation and preparedness must be rejected, for it provided empirical evidence of significant results.

Table 3. Significant Relationship between Teachers' Classroom Environment and Students' Motivation and Preparedness

Variables	Teachers' Classroom Environment	r-value	p-value	Interpretation
Decision				
Students' Motivation and Preparedness	0.870	<0.001	Significant	Reject H0

The significant relationship between teachers' classroom environment and students' motivation and preparedness is a fundamental aspect of the educational landscape. Smith, et.al (2019) said that a well-crafted classroom environment, shaped by the teacher's approach to instruction, organization, and interpersonal dynamics, can profoundly influence students' levels of motivation and preparedness. A positive and supportive classroom setting, where students feel valued, respected, and engaged, serves as a catalyst for increased motivation. Teachers who foster an atmosphere that encourages curiosity, criti-

cal thinking, and active participation are more likely to inspire students to be motivated learners. Furthermore, the classroom environment plays a crucial role in shaping students' preparedness. An organized and conducive learning space, coupled with clear expectations and effective communication from the teacher, contributes to students feeling ready and equipped for their academic pursuits (Balint-Langel Riden, 2022). Conversely, a hostile or unstimulating classroom environment can dampen motivation and hinder students' preparedness. A lack of engagement, unclear instructions, or an un-

supportive atmosphere may diminish students' enthusiasm for learning and readiness to participate in class activities. Therefore, the relationship between teachers' classroom environment and students' motivation and preparedness is symbiotic. Teachers can create an environment that facilitates learning and inspires students to be motivated and prepared contributors to their educational journey. Recognizing and nurturing this relationship is crucial for fostering a positive and practical learning experience.

The Domains of Teachers' Classroom Environment Significantly Influence Students' Moti-

vation and Preparedness

Table 4 depicts the simple regression coefficient analysis of the teachers' classroom environment, significantly influencing students' motivation and preparedness. Domains of teachers' classroom environment, such as teacher-student relationship (0.001), safe and inclusive space (0.010), organized learning environment (0.000), consistent classroom management (0.000), and communication and feedback (0.012), significantly influence students' motivation and preparedness.

Table 4. Regression Coefficient Analysis on Domains of Teachers' Classroom Environment Significantly Influence Students' Motivation and Preparedness

Model	B	Beta	Standard Error	SE	p-value	Decisions
H (Intercept)		4.145	0.079	60.416	0.001	Reject H0
H (Intercept)	0.213	0.175	1.076	0.280	0.201	
Teacher-Student Relationship	0.807	0.107	1.010	0.315	0.001	*Reject H0
Safe and Inclusive Space	0.441	0.108	1.299	0.196	0.010	*Reject H0
Organized Learning Environment	0.202	0.097	2.098	0.038	0.000	*Reject H0
Consistent Classroom Management	0.683	0.086	5.654	0.001	0.000	*Reject H0
Communication and Feedback	0.441	0.108	2.098	0.038	0.012	*Reject H0
R^2		0.873				
F-value		238.897				
p-value		<0.001				

Meanwhile, the R2 value of 0.873 suggests that the domains of teachers' classroom environment explain 87.3 of students' motivation

and preparedness. This provides empirical evidence that the student's motivation and preparedness variability can be accounted for and

explained by the domain's teachers' classroom environment. In addition, the F-value shows all the sums of squares, with regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F-value (238.897) and F-statistic are significant $p < .001$, indicating that the model predicts the student's motivation and preparedness significantly. The domains of teachers' classroom environment significantly influence students' motivation and preparedness across multiple dimensions. Firstly, the emotional domain is crucial as teachers create a supportive and positive atmosphere. An emotionally safe environment encourages students to express themselves, take intellectual risks, and foster a sense of belonging, directly impacting their learning motivation (Balint-Langel Riden, 2022). In the cognitive domain, the clarity of instructional materials, the presentation of challenging yet attainable tasks, and the encouragement of critical thinking contribute to students' preparedness for academic challenges. Teachers who prioritize the intellectual aspect of the classroom promote a

proactive approach to learning (Wolters Brady, 2021). The social domain is equally influential, emphasizing peer interactions and collaborative learning. A classroom encouraging positive social interactions fosters community, impacting students' motivation through social connections and enhancing their preparedness for collaborative projects. Lastly, the physical domain, including the classroom layout and available resources, can significantly affect students' preparedness. An organized and well-equipped learning environment facilitates access to materials, reducing barriers to preparedness (Cuje, 2022).

In summary, the emotional, cognitive, social, and physical domains collectively shape the overall classroom environment and profoundly influence students' motivation and preparedness. Teachers who recognize and address these domains effectively contribute to an enriched educational experience beyond imparting knowledge, nurturing students' intrinsic motivation, and preparing them for academic success.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the findings, conclusions, and recommendations based on the results of the data analysis, discussion, and drawing of implications. Findings are based on the problem's posed statement; conclusions are based on the findings generated, and recommendations are based on the implications of the discussions.

4.1. Findings—The following are the study's findings, as shown in the presentation results, analysis, and discussions. The extent of teachers' classroom environment shows that safe and inclusive space (3.56), organized learning environment (3.56), and teacher-student relationship (3.54) are often manifested. In contrast, communication and feedback (2.80) and consistent classroom management (2.61) are sometimes manifested. This denotes that the extent of the teachers' classroom environment is sometimes manifested and, thus, moderately extensive. The extent of students' motivation

and preparedness shows that academic confidence (3.67), self-advocacy skills (3.59), and goal setting (3.57) are often manifested. In contrast, resilience, adaptability (3.39), time management, and organizational skills (2.95) are sometimes manifested. This denotes the extent to which students' motivation and preparedness are often manifested and, thus, extensive. Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between teachers' classroom environment ($r=0.870$; $p < .001$) and students' motivation and preparedness. Domains of teachers' classroom environment, such as the teacher-student

relationship (0.001), safe and inclusive space (0.010), organized learning environment (0.00), consistent classroom management (0.000), and communication and feedback (0.012), significantly influence students' motivation and preparedness.

4.2. Conclusions—Given the findings of the study presented, the following are the conclusions to wit; The extent of teachers' classroom environment shows that safe and inclusive space, organized learning environment, and teacher-student relationships are often manifested. In contrast, communication feedback and consistent classroom management are sometimes manifested. This denotes that the extent of the teachers' classroom environment is sometimes manifested and, thus, moderately extensive. The extent of students' motivation and preparedness shows that academic confidence, self-advocacy skills, and goal setting are often manifested. In contrast, resilience, adaptability, time management, and organizational skills sometimes manifest. This denotes the extent to which students' motivation and preparedness are often manifested and, thus, extensive. Pearson's Correlation generated a significant correlation between teachers' classroom environment and students' motivation and preparedness. Domains of teachers' classroom environment, such as the teacher-student relationship, safe and inclusive space, organized learning environment, consistent classroom management, and communication and feedback, significantly influence students' motivation and preparedness.

4.3. Recommendations—With the presented conclusions of the study, the following are recommendations to wit;

Public School District Supervisor The supervisor may consider implementing professional development programs for teachers focused on enhancing classroom environments, fostering positive teacher-student relationships, and pro-

moting effective instructional strategies. Additionally, the supervisor could explore ways to allocate school resources based on the study's specific needs. Regular monitoring and support systems can be established to ensure the sustained improvement of teaching practices.

School Principal The principal may prioritize creating a conducive learning environment within the school. This could involve investing in infrastructure improvements, promoting a positive school culture, and encouraging teacher collaboration. Implementing mentorship programs for new teachers to learn from experienced colleagues could promote a positive classroom environment. The school head should work towards maintaining open lines of communication with teachers to address concerns and foster a collaborative approach to school improvement. Teachers May actively engage in professional development opportunities to enhance their teaching skills, focusing on creating a positive classroom environment and strengthening teacher-student relationships. Incorporating student-centered teaching methods, providing constructive feedback, and continuously reflecting on their teaching practices can improve student motivation and preparedness. Collaborative planning sessions among teachers can also facilitate the sharing of effective instructional strategies.

Future Researchers May build upon the current study by further investigating the factors contributing to a positive classroom environment and student motivation. Exploring innovative teaching approaches and assessing the long-term impact of positive teacher-student relationships on student outcomes could be fruitful areas for future research. Researchers should also consider conducting studies in diverse educational settings to provide a more comprehensive understanding of effective educational practices.

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